

N-chlorosaccharin are proposed as active forms of oxidant participating in the oxidation process. We suggest the following mechanism in which the alcohol attacks the active species of oxidant in the rate determining step,

Based on this mechanism the following rate expression can be obtained,

Rate = k_1 [substrate] [oxidant] + $K_2 k_3$ [substrate] [H⁺] [oxidant] and $k_{\text{obs}} = k_1$ [substrate] + $K_2 k_3$ [substrate] [H⁺], which explains first order in substrate and oxidant respectively and fractional order in H⁺. An attempt has been made to evaluate the rate constants k_1 , $K_2 k_3$ and $k_1 + K_2 k_3$ [H⁺] for cyclopentanol and cyclohexanol. The calculated values are given in Table 6.

TABLE 6—CALCULATED VALUES OF k_1 , $K_2 k_3$ AND $k_1 + K_2 k_3$ [H⁺]

Substrate	$k_1 \times 10^3$ l mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	$K_2 k_3 \times 10^3$ l ² mol ⁻² s ⁻¹	$[k_1 + K_2 k_3 [\text{H}^+]] \times 10^3$
Cyclopentanol	1.9	3.12	1.44 at 0.4 M H ⁺
Cyclohexanol	5.0	25.0	1.50 at 0.04 M H ⁺

The kinetic evidence for the oxidation of cyclic alcohols by *N*-bromosaccharin and *N*-chlorosaccharin shows that different types of mechanism is operating in both the cases. This may be attributed due to the difference in electronegativities of the halo substituents¹⁰. Such type of observation was marked by Venkatasubramanian *et al.*^{1,2} during the oxidation of alcohols by *N*-chlorosuccinimide and *N*-bromosuccinimide.

The rate data given in Table 5 shows that under similar experimental conditions, the order of reactivity for all the alcohols studied above 40% (v/v) acetic acid–water is cyclohexanol > cyclooctanol > cycloheptanol > cyclopentanol. Similar order of reactivity is observed in the oxidation of cyclanols by VV.

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Thermodynamics of Ionic Association in Aqueous Solutions of Sodium Salts of some Aromatic Carboxylic Acids using Ion-selective Electrode Technique

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THE newly developed ion-selective electrodes¹ have found very useful application in the study of the ion-association processes in solutions. A recent review² has been published concerning its use in this important area. In an earlier series of publications, we have applied this method to study the association in some important inorganic salts³⁻⁵ and organic salts⁶⁻⁹ in aqueous media.

In this paper, we report the application of the same technique to obtain thermodynamic data of the association process of sodium ion with *m*-hydroxybenzoate, 3,5-dihydroxybenzoate, -gallate, -phthalate and -terephthalate ions in aqueous solutions. Our purpose was to determine whether there is an association taking place or not in these systems, and to determine quantitatively the association constants and other thermodynamic parameters. In this paper we start with the sodium salts as an example of the monovalent salts to enable comparing such organic salts with those of inorganic ones. The values obtained here will be used in any corrections to be needed for the study of the Ca and Mg salts of these same organic ligands

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NOTES

in presence of NaClO₄ or NaCl as inert salts for fixing the various ionic strengths under investigation.

Experimental

The potential measurements were made with a Radiometer PH-M62 digital pH-mV meter equipped with monovalent sodium glass electrode in conjunction with single junction electrode Orion 90-01. The two electrodes were immersed in a double-jacket cell thermostatted at the proper temperature of measurements.

The preparation of the sodium salts, their aqueous solutions, and the experimental procedures were as in the earlier investigations^{9,10}.

Mathematical approach: For the association of sodium ion with *m*-hydroxybenzoate, 3,5-dihydroxybenzoate and -gallate ions, Na⁺ + A⁻ ⇌ NaA

where A⁻ is an organic anion, and the thermodynamic association constant K_A is given by

$$K_A = \frac{[\text{NaA}]}{[\text{Na}^+]_f \cdot [\text{A}^-]_f} \cdot \frac{f_{(\text{NaA})}}{f_{(\text{Na}^+)} \cdot f_{(\text{A}^-)}} \quad (1)$$

where, *f* is the mean activity coefficient of the corresponding species. On the other hand, for the association of sodium with phthalate and terephthalate, two mechanisms may be assumed,

(i) Na⁺ + A²⁻ ⇌ NaA⁻, where A²⁻ may be phthalate or terephthalate; the thermodynamic association constant K_A is given by

$$K_A = \frac{a_{(\text{NaA}^-)}}{a_{(\text{Na}^+)} \cdot a_{(\text{A}^{2-})}} = K \cdot \frac{f_{(\text{NaA}^-)}}{f_{(\text{Na}^+)} \cdot f_{(\text{A}^{2-})}} \quad (2)$$

where, *K* is the stoichiometric association constant. Assuming *f*_(NaA⁻) = *f*_(Na⁺), equation (2) becomes,

$$K_A = K \cdot \frac{I}{f_{(\text{A}^{2-})}} \quad (3)$$

(ii) Na⁺ + A²⁻ ⇌ Na₂A,

$$K_A = \frac{a_{(\text{Na}_2\text{A})}}{a_{(\text{Na}^+)}^2 \cdot a_{(\text{A}^{2-})}} = K \cdot \frac{f_{(\text{Na}_2\text{A})}}{f_{(\text{Na}^+)}^2 \cdot f_{(\text{A}^{2-})}} \quad (4)$$

Assuming *f*_(Na₂A) = 1, equation (4) becomes,

$$K_A = K \cdot \frac{I}{f_{(\text{Na}^+)}^2 \cdot f_{(\text{A}^{2-})}} \quad (5)$$

The K_A values calculated using the above equations were not corrected for any cationic or anionic hydrolysis. In the pH range under investigation the hydrolysis can be safely neglected.

Results and Discussion

It is to be expected that ion-association would be a minimum for the salts of alkali metals with univalent anions. This was found to be true for the sodium salts of *m*-hydroxybenzoic acid and 3,5-dihydroxybenzoic acid, by comparing the voltage (mV) for both the sodium salts with that for NaCl solutions of same concentrations and at the same temperature. However, the sodium salts of gallic, phthalic and terephthalic acids were found to be partially dissociated. In the case of sodium gallate, we assume the association between Na⁺ and carboxylic group to take place in one step, the K_A values are not large but noticeable. These low values may explain why we could not observe any association between Na⁺ ions and the anions of *m*-hydroxybenzoate and 3,5-dihydroxybenzoate. It is obvious that the presence of the OH group in the *para*-position in the case of gallate ion should increase the acidity strength of this acid, thus giving more chance for sodium gallate association.

The remaining two cases are those where two carboxylate groups exist, *i.e.* the phthalate and terephthalate sodium salts. For these two salts, there are two possible mechanisms, (i) and (ii). In the first case, the values K_A for these two salts are

TABLE 1—STOICHIOMETRIC ASSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF SODIUM SALTS USING NaCl AS A STANDARD SOLUTION IN AQUEOUS TETRAMETHYLAMMONIUM CHLORIDE (TMA) SOLUTION AT VARIOUS TEMPERATURES AND IONIC STRENGTHS

Temp. °C	I _s M	K dm ³ mol ⁻¹				
		Gallate	Phthalate Mechanism (i)	Phthalate Mechanism (ii)	Terephthalate Mechanism (i)	Terephthalate Mechanism (ii)
25	0.15	3.89	16.58	219.77	13.83	171.95
	0.20	3.66	15.58	162.54	12.07	114.81
	0.25	3.43	14.55	126.16	11.03	86.49
	0.30	3.41	13.36	99.66	10.22	68.69
35	0.15	4.09	17.47	235.15	14.58	184.38
	0.20	3.70	16.49	171.46	12.98	126.72
	0.25	3.37	15.08	133.03	11.95	96.43
	0.30	3.12	14.06	106.79	11.45	80.36
45	0.15	4.83	18.46	253.38	15.38	197.93
	0.20	4.35	17.10	184.93	14.35	145.06
	0.25	3.98	15.96	143.90	14.03	120.57
	0.30	3.99	14.70	113.70	12.49	90.58

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF SODIUM SALTS OF AROMATIC ACIDS AT VARIOUS TEMPERATURES

Salt	T °C	K _A dm ³ mol ⁻¹	-ΔG°	ΔH°	ΔS°
Gallate	25	5.76 ± 0.53	4.85	2.35	0.023
	35	5.74 ± 1.14	4.48	2.85	0.023
	45	6.65 ± 1.66	5.02	2.35	0.024
Phthalate Mechanism (i)	25	42.40 ± 2.70	9.23	1.67	0.037
	35	44.50 ± 3.10	9.74	1.67	0.038
	45	46.70 ± 3.20	10.20	1.67	0.038
Phthalate Mechanism (ii)	25	682.60 ± 327.20	16.20	2.50	0.063
	35	724.70 ± 350.10	16.90	2.50	0.063
	45	780.10 ± 380.60	17.60	2.50	0.064
Terephthalate Mechanism (i)	25	33.10 ± 1.10	8.70	3.18	0.040
	35	35.90 ± 3.00	9.20	3.18	0.041
	45	39.70 ± 2.60	9.70	3.18	0.041
Terephthalate Mechanism (ii)	25	493.90 ± 291.70	15.40	4.02	0.066
	35	546.20 ± 291.00	16.10	4.02	0.066
	45	621.80 ± 283.50	17.00	4.02	0.067

still small ones. However, the sodium ions are found to be more associated to the phthalate ion than to the terephthalate ion, which is opposite to what one would expect according to the pK_A values¹⁰. This reverse order may be explained on the basis of the inductive effect of the carboxylate group in the *para*-position. In the second case, the K_A values obtained are not acceptable due to the large values of their standard deviations, which exceed 50% in all cases. We, therefore, suggest that only the first association mechanism is acceptable.

Thus only three of the five sodium salts are shown to be associated, namely, Na-gallate, -phthalate and -terephthalate; the other two, namely, Na-*m*-hydroxybenzoate and 3,5-dihydroxybenzoate are completely dissociated.

It is worth noting that the stoichiometric association constants for sodium gallate is comparable to that of the sodium bisulphate^{11,12} ion-pair at the same ionic strength. For example at an ionic strength of 0.21 M at 25°, $K_{(NaHSO_4)} = 3.70 \pm 0.3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ and $K_{(Na-gallate)} = 3.66 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$. On the other hand, the values for Na-phthalate and -terephthalate are much larger than those of NaHSO₄. Thus, the association of sodium salts of inorganic ligands are comparable to those of organic ligand with the same charge under the same conditions.

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Solute-Solvent Interaction Studies of some Solutions Involving Ascorbic Acid

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MULTICOMPONENT solutions play an important role in physiological processes of body fluids and cell equilibria. Ascorbic acid is believed either to promote the secretion of enzymes or create suitable molecular environment for enzymes to act effectively¹. Kaulgud² *et al.* have studied the apparent molar volume, apparent molar compressibility and viscosity of ascorbic acid in water and 0.06 M NaCl at 25°.

The study reported here is a part of the investigations regarding thermodynamic and transport studies of solutions involving ascorbic acid. Some interesting results are expected in the solute-solvent interactions in water and in electrolyte solutions in presence of vitamin C, hence the studies of ascorbic acid in water and different electrolyte solutions at different concentrations were carried out. Properties like molar volume, viscosity and conductance have been studied to interpret the results in terms of solute-solvent interaction in recent past³⁻⁶. In the present communication, results for the studies of viscosity and conductance of solutions consisting of KCl, NaCl and LiCl with ascorbic acid are described.

Experimental

Conductivity water of specific conductance $1.3 \times 10^{-6} \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, was obtained by distilling it thrice over alkaline potassium permanganate. KCl and NaCl (AnalaR) were used without further purification. LiCl (B.D.H.) was purified by crystallising from water, dried for 24 h at 130°, in an oven, and then kept over P₂O₅ in vacuum desiccator before use. Ascorbic acid (AnalaR) was recrystallised from a mixture of methanol-ethyl ether-petroleum ether, dried and kept over anhydrous CaCl₂ in a desiccator.